
Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning for Data Center Operations

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is a technology that became popular recently due to the advancement in how it is used to solve problems. It allows machines to perform cognitive functions like humans because they can perceive, learn, and interact intelligently (Ergen, 2019). This technology has been applied in different spheres of industry to perform work that would have ordinarily been performed by humans and with a lot of positive experience.

This research work aims to explore the possibility of adopting this AI and ML technology in the complex data center facilities operations believing it would achieve the same positive result observed in the other industry where it was implemented. XYZ Data Center, a data center hyperscale service provider is the organization used as the case study for this research.

A mixed methodology combining both qualitative and quantitative was employed in this research and the data collection was limited to the critical operations team of XYZ Data Center. Data was collected through a survey questionnaire and analyzed to get what serves as the results of this research paper. The output shows the strong belief by the participants that AI and ML would improve their operations. Still, there are some concerns about the readiness of the organization in the adoption of the technology.

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1. Introduction

The main driver of the world's economy has been technology since the late 19th century, and this keeps improving year on year. The birth of technology has revolutionized everything from how we work, carry out transactions, propagate communication, transportation and so on (Bahrini and Qaffas, 2019). This has been the main driver of the job market in the 20th century, and this is one of the reasons behind the topic of this research paper. The job market has changed a lot due to technological advancement birthed the era of digitization (Chinoracký and Čorejova, 2019).

This technological advancement has ushered in the digital age in which we find ourselves in this present dispensation. Digitization has revolutionized how things are done and the disruption caused by this revolution changed people's appetite from the old method of getting things accomplished. This new embrace of digitization keeps increasing, putting strain on the existing IT infrastructure, and fueling the need for continuous growth and improvement (Xu, Zhong and Li, 2022). The data center is at the center of digitization as this facility is the main hub of every infrastructure for data storage, processing, and networking that supports the technology (Urbach, et al., 2019). These come in different sizes depending on the level of services the facility supports. The huge number of computing processes in the data center makes it highly energy-intensive, which introduces some complications to the management of these facilities (Obringer, et al., 2021). There is a need to manage for high uptime, high availability, energy efficiency, cost efficiency, and sustainability.

Many different processes require proper coordination for these facilities to run effectively and efficiently to support the various business processes it is designed to support. There are different technologies employed to ensure the different components of the facility work together to deliver on its designed objectives. Based on the ever-increasing demand for data services, there is always a need for upgrades and continuous improvement for these complex processes to meet this growing demand (Cheng, et al., 2018; Bilal, et al., 2018).

Data Centers are the heartbeat of cloud computing, e-commerce, social media, and every other form of digital process (Bilal, et al., 2018). The ever-increasing development and adoption of digital services have caused an increase in the demand for data center services and as these are increasing, the processes surrounding the management and operations of these facilities keep increasing in complexity. Due to many computer applications and processes running in the data center, the facility's energy consumption is huge, and this has drawn the attention of utility service providers and concerned government regulatory bodies. The power consumption of the data center industry in the United States is rated to be 2% of the nation's total energy consumption and 3% of global energy consumption. Ordinarily, 2% or 3% seems small, but this is huge if we consider the total energy consumption of a large country like the United States of America. Three percent of the global energy consumption is approximately 370 Terra Watts, according to a report published by Energy Innovation in partnership with Aspen Global Change Institute (Energy Innovation, 2020). This energy consumption has brought about the question of sustainability. How sustainable is the data center facility and how can this be improved? The rule of thumb approach towards energy sustainability is to make the facility more efficient by reducing energy consumption to a reasonable level. Another approach to this improvement is sourcing the energy required to run the facility from a sustainable source.

The points above make the operation of these facilities complex due to various non-linear components that need to be coordinated to run together seamlessly to achieve high energy efficiency to improve sustainability. The rapid depletion of the ozone layer and the global race towards making the world a better place now and for future generations has brought about recent regulations in Europe that require these facilities to start reporting on sustainability (Judge, 2023). Looking at the impact of AI and ML in the technology space, it would be okay to assume that this technology if employed would bring a tremendous improvement to the operations of the data center facilities.

The introduction of the technology into the complex operations of the data center would provide an opportunity to properly model raw operations data to improve the measurement and control of these metrics to an acceptable range. After this is achieved, the data center can be acclaimed as efficient and sustainable.

This paper will look at the adoption of this technology in two parts:

1. The acceptability of the technology with the considerations of all the positive and the negative attention its evolution has generated globally. Just like every other new technology, the myths around AI seem to be spreading more than the technology and these myths range from, it is going to take our jobs, it is going to kill us, it is going to make us dumb etc (Atkinson, 2018). XYZ Data Center will be used as a case study for this research. The research would be conducted in terms of a survey on the openness of decision-makers within the organization to the adoption of the technology.
2. This research will also assess the general understanding of the key operations team within the organization on artificial intelligence and machine learning technology and the potential positive impact the adoption could have on the operations of their data centers.

The aim and objective of the research work is the introduction of AI and ML technology into complex data center operations with the possibility of improving how the activities below are done:

- Improving the efficiency of data centre energy use.
- Improving data centre infrastructure's resilience.
- Reduced maintenance expenses due to predictive analytics and machine learning
- Elimination of human-caused mistakes and enhancement of quality of service (QoS) by early identification of system breakdowns.
- Enhanced Data Center Safety and Health.
- Understand the operations team's perception of the technology.
- Gauge the readiness of the organization on the deployment of the technology.

2. Literature Review

This literature review will focus on available works on the topic of AI and ML for Data Center operations. In conducting this literature review, a review of some of these works would be done highlighting the research philosophy, research design, methodology, the different findings, and a comparison of what this paper is going to do differently from what has been done in these papers. A review of different papers on any related works on the benefit of AI and ML technology adoption in different ranges of industries which might not be the same as the data center but with similar operational benefits would be carried out. The methodology employed in the literature review for this work is to break down the topic into different aspects of the data center operations and related works in different areas will be explored. Searches were conducted using Google Scholar with a preference set to research works and articles linked to the Anglia Ruskin University library.

In performing the literature review of this research topic, it is essential to conduct an extensive analysis of the different research papers, academic journals, and different industry-based research results. The search was conducted on the topic of AI and Data center operations to get the list of topics and work that have been carried out around the research topic and several relevant papers were presented. It was further scaled down to the year of publication not later than the year 2018. This standard of working within this year 2018 for this research work to ensure the validity and the currency of the paper reviewed.

2.1. Definition of AI and ML

This paper will not be complete if the salient point of the topic is not defined elaborately before going into the study. The technology AI has been around for longer than people can imagine, and the history can be traced to a period before the 18th century (Haenlein and Kaplan, 2019). The first scientific paper on the subject was published in the year 1950 by Alan Turing who wrote on computer machinery and intelligence (George and Walsh, 2022). Technology has been evolving since its discovery and it has gone through many evolutions and enhancements but with little public knowledge except for people who are directly related to working with it. The recent explosion in the publication around AI technology has been brought about by the recent progress made in the areas of robotics and process automation and further enhanced by the growth in appetite for digitization that has been the hallmark of the last few years.

To fully understand the concept of AI, we would need to deal with the words that make up AI in parts, the word artificial in combination with the word intelligence. Intelligence is a quality ascribed to humans due to our capacity to reason situations irrespective of the structure and come up with a logical decision (Lanz, 2000). The term, artificial is a derivative of the fact that the source of intelligence is not biological which is the norm, but from a series of computer codes. AI involves the training of computer machines to understand human intelligence by making the machine go through the same process human acquires knowledge and intelligence (McCarthy, 2007). AI is built to understand complex data, make reasonable judgments and decision from it as well and learn from experience over time just like human does. This characteristic of learning from experience enables AI to gradually improve its accuracy over time.

Machine learning just like AI is used for predictions based on data fed into it and it is constructed to improve with experience as well (Mitchell, 1997). This is a field of artificial intelligence that allows the computer system the ability to learn from experience just like humans

without being programmed. Because technological growth has brought upon us the availability of humungous data, the human mind can't analyze these data with the required speed and accuracy. This is where machine learning comes in to enhance reading complex data using sets of algorithms to learn the way human does (Brown, 2021).

This leads to the question of the relationship between AI and ML. Machine learning tells you what you want to know while AI does the automation by telling you about the rules for the automation. Both terms are used interchangeably especially when discussing big data, and predictive analysis and this is because they are closely related. AI is a technology that comprises a set of different technologies that work together to enable it to function and deliver in line with its design. Machine learning is one such technology that is a subset of AI. The relationship can be further explained by saying AI is a bigger concept that uses ML applications to extract knowledge from data and learn from it to enable it to reason, behave and adapt like humans.

2.1.1. Characteristics of AI and ML

The characteristics of AI and ML are wide, and some are very dependent on the application of the technology. Some of these characteristics could range from connectivity, cognitive ability, and interoperability (Canhoto and Clear, 2020). Some articles listed the characteristics of the technology as its ability to act and think rationally like humans. This has been the main reason behind the popularity attracted by technology in recent years. The ability to make accurate rational decisions and act without human intervention which reduces the potential for human errors has endeared a lot of industry to its use (Yeasmin, 2019).

2.1.2. Application of AI and ML in the Data Center

AI and ML technology has experienced tremendous breakthroughs in every field of business operations from services, education, creative art, music, customer satisfaction, medicine, agriculture, manufacturing etc. (Davenport and Ronanki, 2018). It has been trending with the advent of OpenAI applications like ChatGPT and others due to the ease it has brought to how work is accomplished (Rahaman, 2023). Due to the recent application of this technology to different fields of human endeavour and its subsequent success, it has become a hot topic among data center operators. There have been different considerations about the potential benefit the technology would bring to the industry as well as the risk of its adoption.

There is varying industry-level research about the adoption of the technology and the methodology adopted in these studies varies from quantitative to qualitative. Some have embarked on surveys to understand the different operator's perspectives on the adoption of the technology in their facilities while others have gone as far as performing experimental research to study the potential benefit of the same.

2.2. Related Works

According to an article published by Data Center Knowledge, AI is projected to reshape Data Center operations in 5 different ways namely, physical security, energy management, capacity management and planning, incident response and resolution, and hardware optimization (Tozzi, 2023). There was another article published by Ernst and Young that elaborated on how AI and the Internet of Things (IoT) could help data centers to be greener. The article further expatiated how this could be achieved through data center process automation and energy efficiency because of AI (Thomas, 2022). These applications were further supported by

another article from Data Center Dynamic on the topic “The role of ML and AI in data centers. The limitation of the existing tools being used by the data center was highlighted in the article and the argument about the improvement AI could bring on board through improved data analytics, better operational visibility, improved decision making, improved energy savings, and reduced human errors were presented (Joaquin, 2023).

The list below summarises the areas of AI and ML technology that could be utilized in data center operations:

- Physical Security
- Energy Efficiency
- Availability
- Safety
- Capacity Management
- Risk Management
- Staffing
- Sustainability
- Scalability and Flexibility in Operations
- Optimal Workload Management
- Faster problem detection and resolution
- Reduced Downtime
- Cost Savings
- Data Center Automation
- Predictive maintenance
- Improved resource allocation

These papers are grouped based on the research design and the methodologies employed in the work and on the themes, they were set to address in their hypothesis as listed below:

- AI for Data Center Monitoring
- AI for Energy efficiency improvement
- AI for productivity improvement
- AI for operational efficiency improvement
- AI for security improvement
- AI for improvement in risk identification and mitigation process
- AI for plant maintenance
- AI for cost improvement
- AI for sustainability improvement
- AI for capacity planning improvement
- AI for safety improvement

2.2.1. AI for Data Center Monitoring

This aspect talks more about the monitoring of the data center infrastructure, and this considers the quantity of equipment to measure, the data type, the volume of data, the frequency of data collection and the mode of collection. There are various research articles on this subject, and they all share some similarities in the research design and methodology.

According to a paper titled “AIOps Architecture in Data Center Site Infrastructure Monitoring” (Dong, 2022), research was conducted in China centred around the telecoms industry taking into consideration the number of sites requiring monitoring, the data collection method and the frequency of data collected. This research focuses on the technical part of the monitoring and does not consider how service could be enhanced through the technology. The advantages and disadvantages of the existing method were compared with the employment of AIOps for this process and it was in this process that the hypothesis of the paper was stated.

The disadvantages like the large data volume of manual data processing, longer mean time to error detection and the mean time to repair were established and the benefits of achieving the same with AIOps were outlined. These benefits include an improvement in the quality of the product, increased productivity, reduction in mean time to error detection and mean time to maintenance.

This research article’s design is more of the quantitative type and very practical in the sense that it includes all the technicalities relating to the data algorithm, data modelling design, database type, historical data handling, real-time data handling, data conversion method and data loss prevention method used.

Another study touched on the reason for the use of AI monitoring in the data center as the result of the complexity of the infrastructure that makes it impossible to manually manage the different variables. This makes automation a must-have to efficiently manage the infrastructure to meet the required service levels (Gulenko, et al., 2020). This study was not just limited

to monitoring and controls but also touched on the area of the level of automation required in the AI-controlled system highlighting what level of human interaction is required in the monitoring and control process (Wilson and Daugherty, 2018). The area however not covered in the research papers is the exploration of the data center monitoring through artificial intelligence. This research will investigate the benefits that can be derived through the collaboration of the technology and human interaction (Gupta, et al., 2022).

2.2.2. AI for Energy efficiency improvement

Another paper highlights a practical scenario of the employment of AI and ML for the improvement of energy consumption in an already energy-efficient data center facility. This research was built on the hypothesis that the engagement of AI and ML in the operation of the infrastructure within the facility would further improve the energy efficiency of the facility (Todd, et al., 2021). This was technical research that captured data extensively from not just the facility equipment but also the network usage, server CPU utilization and all other activities that contribute to the data center energy consumption. These data were used to train the model to improve the overall energy efficiency of the facility to support the hypothesis. It was however easy to find the motivation for this type of study as this project was undertaken in a research facility with the financial power of the government and other hyperscalers in the industry.

What was however not touched on in this paper that would be addressed in this research is the motivation for different operators to undertake this type of AI engagement putting into consideration the subject of budget, required skilled manpower, operational impact, and other myths around the deployment of the technology.

The subject of energy consumption of data centers has been a major concern to the various operators based on how energy-intensive these facilities are and their direct contribution to carbon emissions. Some research works deal with this problem by looking at the impact the AI technology could have on improving the energy efficiency of these facilities and studies have shown that the majority, about 50% of the energy consumed in the data center is from cooling (Ilager, 2021). It has been estimated that the data center energy consumption will increase to 974 TWh by 2030 according to a publication by the International Journal of Green Technology in 2019 (Andrae, 2019). The study focuses on the methodology of improving data center energy efficiency through a proper resource allocation process that leverages AI technology to achieve this feat (Ilager, 2021). This aspect of the paper's review focuses on the gains that could be achieved by leveraging the technology to achieve energy efficiency as well as addressing the challenges the deployment would face. It does not however address the challenge of the willpower of the operators on the deployment of this technology due to cost and budgetary constraints which would be addressed in the research work.

The study "AI-Driven Prediction-Based Energy-Aware Fault Tolerant Scheduling Strategy for Cloud Data Centers" worked on a new scheduling scheme for improving data center energy efficiency and fault tolerance. This study uses AI for workload estimation and allocates resources efficiently. Data used for the study was gathered through journals, articles and abstracts and did not reference any real-life data (A. Marahatta, et al., 2021). What the research paper would do differently from this study is use real-life data from a mixed methodology to achieve the same result.

2.2.3. AI for Data Center Digital Twin Enhancement

Digital twin is the virtual representation of the real-life object for a better understanding of the underlying physical process of the object towards improvement, optimization and streamlining (VanDerHorn and Mahadevan, 2021) (Rathore, et al., 2021). Materials from various academic sources were used to get information about what has been published in this field and analysis of these was done through a descriptive method. The whole research paper was based on experimentation within the industry (Rathore, et al., 2021). The digital twin in the data center is also referred to as smart DC (Zhang, et al., 2022). The combination of the digital twin technology and artificial intelligence has been observed to bring a lot of improvement to data center operations ranging from power and cooling optimization to other operational efficiency (Liu, et al., 2021). This energy-saving reduction was observed in the introduction of AI technology to the traditional system and a savings of 41.07% was achieved on the refrigeration energy consumption (Liu, et al., 2021).

While digital twins brought the digital representation of the facilities to life and improved the human interaction with the various complex equipment required to maintain balance in the data center facilities, artificial intelligence has made it possible to achieve improvement in the energy management system of these smart buildings. AI helped to achieve this through a series of data collection, training, and testing of the model through several iterations (Agostinelli, et al., 2021).

2.2.4. AI for Energy Optimization

A data center facility needs to be energy efficient for reasons ranging from environmental friendliness, because of net carbon footprint reduction, to cost reduction for business profitability purposes. The energy efficiency of a data center facility is dependent on several factors such as the energy efficiency of the IT equipment, the supporting facility equipment, the age of the equipment and the automation of the control process. The improvement in the efficiency of these facilities has been achieved traditionally through the means of replacing the legacy equipment with a newer energy-efficient model, the introduction of a specialized control system that is reactive and the use of renewable energy. The proliferation of AI and ML technology has revolutionized how this is achieved in recent times in the different sectors of the industrial and services industry. The introduction of AI which brought about an intelligent way of managing complex systems beyond the capacity of the human mind has improved energy efficiency management.

AI is an effective method of energy optimization as it is predictive, and it can make informed decisions from complex data obtained from the equipment. This is more effective than the traditional method of improving energy efficiency as it is predictive. The traditional method adjusts parameters based on a set point while AI learns from trends and experiences and accurately predicts when to adjust the set point to achieve the set energy efficiency goal (Lu, et al., 2020).

2.2.5. AI for data center security improvement.

Security is an important component of the data center facility due to the importance of the information stored in the facility. A security breach in a data center could have an immeasurable consequence with an unquantifiable cost. Security in the data center can be subdivided into digital and physical security. Digital security or IT security entails how the organization's assets such as the computers, servers, switches, network, and data are protected from

unauthorized access. When it comes to IT security, it is very important to use the right tool to ensure the information is well secured. The emergence of cloud computing has introduced further vulnerability to the information that is being transmitted in the digital space and this has made it imperative to improve on the modalities for ensuring an organization's important information is secured from hackers who are getting more sophisticated by the day. There is a huge volume of information moving around in the internet space because of users increased appetite for digital resources and this has increased the complexity of information security management methodology. The conventional ways of security management have been exposed to varying degrees of vulnerability and no longer adequately provide the protection needed. A recent solution to this has been the adoption of AI-based safety strategies and this has proven more effective than the traditional method (Kavitha, et al., 2021). Due to the intelligent way the AI model works, it has proven effective in preventing recurrent threats as well as predicting and mitigating budding threats. The methodology employed in this research is experimental as samples were collected from a real-life scenario to draw the model for the findings and the result was published.

It has been observed that most research around AI and security has been focused on IT security and experience have shown that cyber-attacks are not the only way information is stolen but the same level of devastation could be achieved through physical security breach as well (Yang, et al., 2022). The aspect of physical security revolves around preventing physical threats to the data center facility which ranges from access control methods, and CCTV cameras, to setting up multi-layered physical barriers with security guards monitoring and managing all these processes. The emergence of AI into the physical security space has brought about a lot of enhancement to the way things are done and human error has been reduced to a bare minimum. AI can detect a security breach way faster and acts to prevent and activate all the necessary security protocols way faster than any smart human.

As regards risk identification, it is easier for AI to monitor and detect risk when dealing with huge volume of data. It would be difficult for humans to identify risk from thousands of registered occurrences with error while this would be simple for AI. Because AI learns from experience, it can gather data, scan, and analyze to identify risk including positive harmful traffics, and configuration error in a quick and very efficient way.

3. Research Design and Methodology

3.1. Identifications of questions to be addressed by the research paper.

The topic of AI and ML for Data Center operations which is the subject of this dissertation is set to answer some questions in the operations of the data center facility. There have not been many academic papers written specifically about the subject as the Data Center domain is new to the academic circle though this has been popular in the last 2 decades in the information technology industry. The Data Centre could be defined as a facility that houses the organization's critical computer applications and data. This is the facility that forms the infrastructure upon which the backbones of information technology for organizations are built (Kant, 2009). The importance of these facilities to the business operations of any organization cannot be overemphasized based on the reasons above.

This research paper is set to answer pertinent questions about the effect/impact of deploying AI/ML in the operations of data center facilities. The following questions are expected to be addressed by this research paper.

- How would you rate the current level of automation in your data center?
- Would AI and ML be useful tools for your data center operations?
- What are the areas in your data center operations you think AI can bring improvement?
- Would you trust AI/ML to make operational decisions in your data center?
- Do you think AI and ML can improve your data center's energy efficiency?
- Do you think AI and ML improve your data center's sustainability?
- Do you think AI and ML will improve your asset performance management process?
- Would AI and ML technology deployment improve your site's security?
- Do you think AI and ML technology deployment can improve your organization's customer experience?
- Do you think AI and ML technology implementation in data center operations would improve operator safety?
- Do you think the existing data collected in the data center operations is enough to implement AI/ML technology for data center operations?
- Do you think the existing IT staff are familiar with the AI technology?
- What role do you think the budget would play in the potential adoption of AI technology deployment in your organization?
- Do you think that AI can replace the role humans play in your operations?
- Would your organization be willing to implement AI and ML as an experiment or do you want to wait till this becomes an industry trend?
- What do you think is hindering your organization from implementing this technology to its data center operations?

By the end of this paper, it is expected that most of the questions above should have been answered in part or in full.

3.2. Research Approach

This study will be carried out using a combination of the three design methodologies, quantitative, qualitative, and mixed method. This paper will be in two parts, The first part will be to survey of the XYZ Data Center data center which is being used as a case study, and the

second part will look at available experimental research works on AI for data center operations that have been carried out by different similar industry giants and hyperscalers. In the first part, I will be looking at the potential positive impact the adoption of AI and ML technology would bring to Data Center operations in line with the hypothesis of this paper. This would involve conducting exploratory findings from the survey being carried out. The second part would investigate the adoption and acceptability of the technology for data center operations and would also analyze different existing papers that used both interpretivism and positivism approaches in the concept of their research design.

In continuation of the above, the process of data collection would be both from the survey as well as existing available research works that have been carried out by respected industry giants and some industrial professional educational bodies.

3.3. Research Design

This research is geared towards exploring the benefits that the adoption of AI and ML could bring to data center operations. The research would utilize quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods in its approach. This paper will carry out an in-depth analysis of the current system being used in data center operations, considering their benefits and limitations. It would also consider the acceptability of the technology for daily operations as spelt out in the survey questions. Assessment of data centers that are already utilizing AI and ML technology for their operations would be done and the benefits derived from utilizing the technology would be shown.

This study will utilize XYZ Data Center as a case study in line with the aim and objective of this paper. The reasons for choosing XYZ as a case study are as stated below:

- Ease of data collection.
- Getting access to the appropriate demography in the data center industry.
- The data collection would be easy to manage as participants are known and this would ease the follow-up process.
- Getting management buy-in would be easy and the result would prove beneficial to the organization as it could be utilized as an input into the organizational continuous improvement process.
- Access to existing performance data would be easy and for comparison.

3.4. Data Collection and Analysis Method

The diagram below is a representation of the data collection and analysis method employed in this research paper.

Data was collected using a survey questionnaire that would employ both quantitative and qualitative methods. Question styles would range from dichotomous to qualitative feedback bringing further overview of why the selected options were chosen by the participants. The qualitative aspect gives insight to the researcher of what participants think of the adoption of the technology and its believed attending benefits. This would also provide oversight of the different areas of the organization's operations that the participant would be open to adopting the technology.

The data collected were analyzed using both statistical and thematic method. Statistical method was used for the quantitative data collected in form of yes or no answered to some part of survey questions with their outputs graded as percentages. The result derived from inferential statistics was used to test the hypothesis of the study. Thematic analysis was used for the qualitative responses in the survey for the investigation, identifications and recording of patterns in the responses and subsequent grouping into themes (Snyder, 2019). This system helped in breaking down the contents into themes or categories that appears repeatedly (Ritchie, Spencer, and O'Connor, 2003). This inductive analysis of the result of the survey was carried out as it is expected to give improved clarity of the reasons behind the participant's choices. The inductive analysis was used as compensation for the data derived from the deductive analysis of the questionnaire. This system is employed as the answers requested from the participants of the survey did not just end with a yes or no answer but also followed up by questions for the participants to explain reasons for their answers.

4. Research Findings

This survey was conducted within XYZ Data Center to confirm the hypothesis of this research paper that AI and ML would have the same positive impact they had on information technology and the operational technology space in data center operations. The data center operation has been plagued with some challenges that this paper believes would be solved by the adoption of artificial intelligence and machine learning technology in its operations.

4.1. Research Questions

Some of the problems within the industry within the purview of the data gathered by this research survey questionnaires are listed below:

1. Complexity in operations management
2. Safety of data center operators
3. Automation complexity
4. Sustainability
5. Physical security
6. Capacity planning
7. Efficiency improvement
8. Human error elimination
9. Skilled staff shortage

In line with the above problems in mind, a set of sixteen survey questions was drafted and sent out to participants within XYZ Data Center, a Data Center service provider this is used for this case study and a total of 17 responses were received as shown in the appendix section. This survey is in no way technical, but it is set to get the level of acceptability of the technology as well as the level of awareness of the data center operational employees.

4.1.1. How would you rate the current level of automation in your data center?

The terms artificial intelligence and automation has been used interchangeably in recent time, but they are not the same. Automation is the ability of machines or equipment to work with minimal or no human intervention. AI on the other hand is the ability to make the machine intelligent and reason like a human in executing its work by learning from experience just as humans do hence the word artificial (Shekhar, 2019). Artificial intelligence needs some level of automation to work and to produce the desired result and that is the idea behind the first question in the survey trying to know the level of automation within the XYZ's data center.

When the operations management team within the organization was asked to rate the level of automation in their data centers, 58% of the participants rated this as a medium, 23.5% rated this as low and only 17.6% rated this high as shown in the chart below (Figure 1).

How would you rate the current level of automation in your data center?

17 responses

The answers could be interpreted in different ways, but this paper did not intend to pursue further the reasons behind participants' responses to the level of automation in their facilities. This question is a fallout of the complexity of the data center operations containing different equipment that must work together for the facility to function effectively. Because of this complexity, the data center facility relies heavily on automation to be able to maintain the required standard and ensure the facility is delivering on its metrics. The introduction of AI and ML into its operations is to enhance automation and make the facility more efficient based on the predictive ability that this technology would be bringing into its operations. This result indicates the level of trust or comfort the operators have in their level of existing automation and hence the readiness for this revolutionary technology.

4.1.2. Would AI and ML be useful tools for your data center operations?

The next question is about AI and ML being useful tools for the operations of the data center and out of 17 participants, who responded, 82.4% agreed that it would be a useful tool while only 17.3% disagreed (Figure 2). This shows that most of the operations management team believes in the hypothesis of this paper.

Would AI and ML be useful tools for your data center operations?

17 responses

This question would not have been complete without further diving deep into why the participants chose their different options in the survey answers. The quest to find this led to a follow-up question to better understand the reasons behind their choices.

- Mechanical and energy efficiency – This reason is quite understandable as some Data Centers have applied AI and ML into their operations since as early as 2008 and they have been able to record some results (Smolaks, 2023). This has been integrated into the tools used in monitoring and controlling the mechanical equipment involved in environmental setpoint manipulations to optimize cooling and power efficiency. Mechanical cooling consumes about one-third of the total energy in the data center, and this is not a surprise why the attention on energy efficiency improvement is focused on the cooling systems. AI has proven better at improving the efficiency of cooling systems than the traditional method as reported by research on intelligent refrigeration system deployment (Yang, et al., 2018).
- Controls and monitoring – The main tool used for this is the Data Center Infrastructure Management (DCIM) tool, which is utilized to measure, monitor, manage, and control the data center energy consumption and utilization (Gustafsson, et al., 2018). Some of the vendors offering this solution have started integrating AI into the application's operations. This is helpful with threat assessment, fault prediction, fault prevention, energy efficiency, network optimization and capacity planning (Smolaks, 2022).
- Capacity planning – Another point from the analysis of the reason given is capacity planning. This technology has proven effective in data center capacity planning as proven by Facebook in their data center in Sweden (Islam, et al., 2019). This technology when deployed can be used to predict how a data center would operate in the long and this input would help the operator in planning properly for future capacity demand (Le, et al., 2016).
- Diagnostic and self-heal – This can be defined as the ability to recover from faults or glitches after self-diagnosis without human intervention. Systems with this capability can make decisions because they can recover to normalcy from fault, and they are believed to be able to support humans with decision-making (Ghosh, et al., 2007). The advent of ChatGPT in the technological space has proven the effectiveness of AI in this regard.

4.1.3. What are the areas in your data center operations that you think AI and ML can bring improvement?

This question garnered 14 responses from the 17 participants and various answers align with the hypothesis of this study. Below is the list of responses obtained from the analysis done on the replies:

- Mechanical infrastructure would benefit more from the technology given that they are more reactive to load and weather conditions. This is one of the points mentioned in the problem statement of this research work and the area that was proposed AI and ML could improve.
- Facility's physical security
- Reduced equipment downtime through predictive analysis
- Controls and diagnostic

- Maintenance and maintenance planning
- Operational decision making

4.1.4. Would you trust AI/ML to make operational decisions in your data center?

One of the main reasons why AI has gained recent popularity is its ability to make intelligent decisions with little to zero human intervention. This question was asked in the survey as regards operational decision-making with the data center and the response shows that 70.6% of the participants which is twelve (12) out of the seventeen (17) participants agree to allow AI to make operational decisions. The remaining 35.3% did not agree with this idea.

Would you trust AI/ML to make operational decisions in your data center?

17 responses

A follow-up question was asked as to why the participants would allow AI to make decisions as well as why those who answered no would not allow it. There are various reasons given and the reasons are as analyzed below starting with the “yes” answers followed by the “no”.

The integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning in operational processes necessitates the incorporation of a decision engine that offers insights and recommendations to human operators. The system should have modifications that have minimal impact, effective communication, and well-defined escalation procedures. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) systems are required to exhibit a high level of precision and dependability in their predictions and judgments. To ensure constant achievement of desired results, these systems must undergo comprehensive testing and validation processes. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques has the potential to enhance the efficiency of operators, hence minimizing the necessity for extensive investigation of previous data while addressing troubleshooting problems. The total number of personnel responsible for operations should remain constant, however, the implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to enhance the productivity and effectiveness of operators.

The efficacy of AI/ML technology in large-scale essential operations remains unproven, and its reliance on AI/ML systems is characterized by a limited track record. The utilization of this tool is recommended for operational decisions with lower levels of risk, and its implementation

should be gradually extended to operations with higher levels of risk. The lack of understanding in AI decision-making processes can heighten the potential for adverse consequences. The implementation of dual verification is imperative, and it is essential for artificial intelligence (AI) systems to dynamically respond to the prevailing conditions within data centers.

4.1.5. Do you think AI and ML can improve your data center's energy efficiency?

XYZ's critical operations management team believes AI and ML can improve their data center's energy efficiency by 94.1% meaning sixteen out of the seventeen survey participants answered yes. Only a participant did not believe this technology can bring any improvement based on the belief that data centers are more reactive than predictive.

17 responses

The reasons behind the yes answers are as stated below:

- Mechanical infrastructure – There have been cases of AI and ML being used for the improvement of efficiency of the cooling infrastructures in the data center. AI can monitor and control energy consumption within the data center. ML algorithms can analyze energy usage patterns and suggest strategies for optimizing cooling power consumption to reduce operational costs and environmental impact. This technology has been used by some hyperscalers with positive results and these results have been made public. Google was able to consistently achieve 40% energy savings on the cooling infrastructure through the aid of AI and ML technology (Evans and Gao, 2016). Another hyperscaler that has successfully utilized this solution to improve its data center cooling efficiency is Facebook. Facebook started growing immensely in 2009 and this resulted in the growth of its data centers as well. This left the operators and other stakeholders with no option but to innovate to improve efficiency and AI and ML were deployed with positive results (Dhadve, 2017). Microsoft also deployed AI and ML in their data centers in 2021 to help reduce water and energy usage and hence improve efficiency (Walsh, 2022).
- Another reason given is the fact that AI can consider many factors and develop a solution based on facts backed by data, unlike humans who are prone to human feelings behind the decision. AI decision is fact-based and not emotion-driven and thereby reduces the human error of judgment to near zero. It identifies data trends that could guide changes in operation. An AI can analyze large data sets and propose changes in seconds that have traditionally taken a human or team months to accomplish.

- Proper maintenance on equipment can reduce downtime, ensure that the equipment is operating at nominal standards and forecast the need to replace aging or end-of-life equipment.
- Optimizing equipment setpoints, SOO programming, etc.

4.1.6. Do you think AI and ML improve your data center's sustainability?

Sustainability has become an important subject globally due to recent happenings in the world. There are reports of the north pole ice reduction due to global warming among other effects of the depletion of the ozone layer protecting the earth from the heat of the sun. Data Centers have been at the receiving end of public criticism due to their energy and water consumption which is relatively high in comparison with other industries.

A total of 13 participants representing 76.5% of the overall participants in the survey agree that AI and ML would improve their facility's sustainability metrics. The 23.5% that disagree believe that sustainability is driven by human behaviours rather than technology while some believe that this should be driven by processes.

Do you think AI and ML improve your data center's sustainability?

17 responses

Those in agreement stated many reasons behind their choices and an analysis of their different reasons is listed below:

Because AI relies heavily on data, the data collection of various data from different designs and systems would eventually enable it to come up with interesting sustainable equipment selection and maybe design changes. The fact that decisions are made with data will enhance the accuracy of the findings better than any human can do. The complexity of the system in question would make it impossible for a human to handle without errors and AI and ML are built for managing complexity with little margin for error. An AI can analyze large data sets and propose changes in seconds that have traditionally taken a human or team months to accomplish.

AI could lower energy usage through its intelligent predictive capability and fast response to lower power usage effectiveness (PUE), carbon usage effectiveness (CUE) and water usage effectiveness (WUE) metrics to ensure that the facility is using resources efficiently and within limits. More efficient use of energy in the mechanical plant equals a more sustainable data center.

4.1.7. Do you think AI and ML will improve your asset performance management process?

The asset management process in the data center is very crucial as this is the process used in maintaining the accurate inventory of assets. This is not just limited to inventory maintenance but is tied to availability maintenance as real-time tracking helps in ensuring the critical spares are always available on site. Asset tracking in data centers can be a complex undertaking due to their huge size and the high amount of equipment (Brignone, et al., 2007). Automation of the process with the inclusion of AI and ML would improve the process and eliminate human error which is the bane of the traditional process (Yuan, Jiang and Pan, 2022).

In response to this question, 15 of the participants representing 88.2% agree that this technology would improve their asset management performance. Only 2 respondents believe that AI and ML would not improve their data center's asset management performance.

Do you think AI and ML will improve your asset performance management process?

17 responses

Analysis of the answers shows that the respondents who picked yes made their choice based on the reasons below:

- Effective life-cycle replacement analysis – AI's prediction capability would make early detection of assets prone to failure easy, and subsequently notify the operators for prompt replacement procurement.
- Efficient asset usage – This would aid in the efficient usage of assets as this technology would improve the recognition of asset efficiency ratios which helps when making budget decisions.

The participants who did not agree to AI and ML improving their data center asset management had issues with the amount of data available for the model to make predictions that would translate to this improvement.

4.1.8. Would AI and ML technology deployment improve your site's security?

Physical and cyber security is critical in the operations of data centers to safeguard the organization's assets and sensitive information. We are in an era where data is the new gold, and this is the target of hackers who are always looking for unsuspecting or vulnerable prey to profit from (Farkas, 2017).

Ten people representing 58% of the respondents align with the hypothesis that AI and ML technology would improve their site's security while the remaining 41.2% percent are of contrary opinion.

Would AI and ML technology deployment improve your site's security?

17 responses

Based on the nature of the XYZ Data Center's business, the response to this question was more from the physical security perspective as the client is responsible for their information security. Analysis of the result shows that participants with yes answers believe the technology is already being used for the enhancement of physical security devices and processes. One of the areas AI is being used for security is CCTV cameras and intrusion alarm monitoring. AI can be trained to detect if an intruder is human or animal and can assess the threat level by scanning for weapons on the intruder.

On the process aspect, it is being used to reduce false positive alarms which is a major problem with the perimeter monitoring systems. It could initiate a lockdown process in case of life-threatening dangers and as well as promptly alert the concerned authority. It also reduces human error which could be because of fatigue or the security guard zoning out. The negative answers could not see how AI would improve physical security as they believe a lot of the actions required in physical security are more reactive than predictive.

4.1.9. Do you think AI and ML technology deployment can improve your organization's customer experience?

Before going into the results of the survey, it is imperative to talk about what customer experience in the data center industry means. Customer experience can be related to the perception of a customer about an organization after contact. Customer experience happens during contact as well as their continuous interaction with the company (Meyer and Schwager, 2007). In the data center industry, customer experience has to do with trust in terms of adherence to all contractual service levels like availability, uptime, efficiency, security, and scalability.

10 respondents believed AI would improve the organization's customer experience while the remaining 7 did not believe the technology would have any impact.

Do you think AI and ML technology deployment can improve your organization's customer experience?

17 responses

There are various reasons stated by those who believe in the impact of technology on customer experience and below are the findings from the analysis of the reasons.

Faster response time to customer's request – Unlike humans, AI is very fast in analyzing data and this would be an advantage when it comes to customer request analysis and prompt assignment of resources to address. This edge will also play a role in the analysis of customer's online interaction and be able to advise operators based on findings that could improve customer experience. Another benefit of this is the anticipation of customers' needs based on experience and prompt attention.

Those who answered no believe customer experience is built around people and processes which they assumed is beyond the capability of AI. They are in support of the thought process that aligns with the traditional method that customers experience is face-to-face human interaction and AI would take that away.

4.1.10. Do you think an AI and ML technology implementation in data center operations would improve operator safety?

Safety is one of the most important policies in the XYZ data center as it is critical for the organization that all employee returns home to their loved ones safely after every day's task. The organization has taken on the responsibility of safety first in all their operations to protect its most valued asset which is the people (XYZ, 2023). The target is to achieve zero incidents through their Plan, Do, Check, Act philosophy. This philosophy is implemented throughout their different aspects of offerings ranging from design, construction, and operations.

Data center operations teams are exposed to various safety hazards in performing their daily hazards. There are various sources of energy available in the facilities ranging from electrical, mechanical, and pneumatic, to sound etc. If safety is not taken seriously, it exposes even the most professional operator to the risk of injury.

The question of whether AI and ML adoption in the safety processes could improve operator safety was asked as part of the survey question. Responses from participants show that 14 people out of 17 representing 82.4% believe the technology would improve operator's safety while the remaining 3 (17.6%) disagree.

Do you think an AI and ML technology implementation in data center operations would improve operator safety?

17 responses

A further deep dive into the reasons behind these responses reveals why the participants made their choices. The analysis of the reasons behind the choices of the participants who responded yes are as stated below:

1. Auto-detection of errors in procedures that could expose operators to safety risks. Simple errors in procedures like failure to lock out alternate sources of energy or operations of the wrong switch or breaker could have fatal consequences on the operator. These two are some of the numerous human errors that the proper application of AI and ML technology could help prevent in the data center.
2. Fast detection or prediction of faulty equipment and prompt isolation is another area in the technology that could add value to the safe operations of the data center facility.
3. Real-life monitoring and data-driven predictive insight into the various processes with the potential for failure is another way accidents can be prevented in the data center workspace.

The respondents who answered no, believe data center operations are built around the operator reacting to issues as they surface and not predicting.

4.1.11. Do you think the existing data collected in the data center operations is enough to implement AI/ML technology for data center operations?

There is a lot of data collected in the data center for the smooth running of the facility's automated process. The PID feedback loop used in controls and maintaining setpoint depends heavily on data from various equipment running in the data to make accurate calculations to achieve its set objective. The functionality of AI technology is all about data and lots of it. Data is the reason behind AI and ML prediction, and it is the source of its intelligence (Sundblad, 2018). For AI to be successful, it needs lots of data and this is what makes it more effective than the traditional way of doing things. This leads this research to the question of whether the existing data available in the data center is enough for the implementation of the AI and ML technology in the XYZ Data Centers data center facility.

Of the 17 participants in this study, 13 of them representing 76.5% believe the data available generated at their various facilities is not enough for building an AI model for the facility's operations. Only 4 respondents believe there is enough data in their facilities to successfully build and train an AI model.

Do you think the existing data collected in the data center operations is enough to implement AI/ML technology for data center operations?

17 responses

A follow-up question was asked about the top 3 additions the respondents would make to increase the volume of data generated to the standard required to build an AI model and the analysis of their inputs is as stated below.

1. More data from facility equipment
2. More data from IT equipment to the level of server processors
3. More data not directly related to the operations of the equipment like vibration monitoring of motors and pump frames.
4. More accurate data
5. Increased data storage capacity to keep historical data longer than the statutory requirement of 90. The availability of historical data would prove useful in training algorithms to understand normal patterns and behaviours.

4.1.12. Do you think the existing IT staff are familiar with the AI technology?

Processes and technology do not run in isolation, it depends on competent people for its success, and this is also applicable to AI and ML deployment. Research conducted by EY on the importance of AI to company success and the impact of skilled personnel on the deployment shows that a lack of skilled personnel is a huge barrier to AI success in most organizations (Vidu, et al., 2020).

This question was asked as part of this research paper's survey question and 64.7% of the respondents believe the existing IT staff in the organizations are not quite familiar with the technology while the remaining 35.3% believe otherwise.

Do you think the existing IT staff are familiar with the AI technology?

17 responses

No follow-up question was asked on the reason for these choices, but this led to the next question in this survey that is believed would add more value to the outcome of the research paper.

4.1.13. If you do not, do you think this can negatively impact the deployment of the technology?

Most respondents, 12 representing 70.6% to be precise think this can negatively impact the adoption of the technology while the remaining 29.4% think it wouldn't. Despite the numerous benefits of AI to the operations of any industry, the lack of technical expertise is listed as one of the reasons why organizations do not derive the full benefit of the applications. The technical acumen required for the modelling and training of artificial intelligence cannot be over-emphasized and the absence of this might result in wasted funds and effort (Merhi, 2023).

If you do not, do you think this can negatively impact the deployment of the technology?

17 responses

4.1.14. Do you think that budget would play an important role in the potential adoption of AI technology deployment in your organization?

One of the reasons listed in a research paper published by the International Journal of Information Management as a critical factor impacting the successful deployment of artificial

intelligent technology in an organization is high cost (Merhi, 2023). This is represented by the budgetary questions asked as part of this paper's survey question. This question was included based on the topography of the survey as organization decision-makers are included in the survey participants.

Out of the 17 respondents to the survey, 16 believe that budget will play an important role in adopting the technology while only 1 respondent believes otherwise.

Do you think budget would play an important role in the potential adoption of AI technology deployment in your organization?

17 responses

4.1.15. Do you think that AI can replace the role humans play in your operations?

Since the emergence of ChatGPT which brought about the recent media sensation on the AI technology, there have been numerous debates about the possibility of AI replacing humans in doing some jobs. This has attracted both positive and negative reactions globally from technology enthusiasts as well as the nonchalant. There have been numerous research and surveys on this topic with varying responses depending on the demography.

This same question was asked in the survey from the XYZ Data Centers operations team and the result is as shown below.

Do you think that AI can replace the role humans play in your operations?

17 responses

Only 1 person out of the 17 participants believes AI could replace humans but a larger percentage believes it wouldn't while the remaining respondents think maybe. The result of this question cannot be complete without further knowing the reasons behind these choices. A follow-up question was asked on the reasons for these choices and the analysis of the responses is summarized below:

1. The yes respondent believes automation is primarily built to replace humans accomplishing tasks.

For the No responses:

- AI can still not be fully trusted to make decisions based on some unforeseen software glitches.
- AI is supposed to enhance humans in the decision-making process as some decisions can only be made by humans. Some physical works are beyond software that only humans can do.

Would your organization be willing to implement AI and ML as an experiment or will the organization be more willing to wait until this becomes an industry trend?

There are many real-life test research in the data center industry on AI being used for data center operations. Some are carried out in purpose-built laboratories for such tests just like the test performed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory in Denver, Colorado (Todd, et al., 2021). Some big players in the cloud computing world like Google, Microsoft and Meta have also built data centers to carry out this test with results made available in the public internet space (Jones, 2018).

When the XYZ Data Centers operations team was asked about their willingness to implement the technology as an experiment, only 4 participants answered yes while 2 respondents were unwilling. Most of the survey participants are not decided yet as 11 people answered maybe.

Would your organization be willing to implement AI and ML as an experiment or will the organization be more willing to wait until this becomes an industry trend?

17 responses

4.1.16. What is hindering your organization from implementing this technology to their data center operations?

Many challenges are hindering a lot of organizations from implementing AI and ML technology in their operation. According to a report published by Forbes, barriers like governance, data quality due to inconsistency of data, the substantial cost of deployment and the time required to achieve full deployment (Shah, 2022). Another research paper published on AI and its business values stated the inhibitors to the technology adoption as organizational readiness, employee trust, environmental peer influence, organizational culture, and compatibility with existing business technology (Enholm, et al., 2022).

This question was asked by the XYZ Data Centers operations team as part of the research question to bring it home in line with the aim of this research paper, the responses received are as analyzed below:

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technologies inside organizational settings presents several obstacles, encompassing financial considerations, the absence of well-established technological infrastructure, uncertainties around accessibility, and constraints in terms of data availability. The hurdles in applying these technologies include a lack of specialist knowledge, an aversion to change, and an inadequate data infrastructure.

Moreover, the presence of corporate bureaucracy might result in a state of inactivity, although the actual evidence supporting the correlation between the use case and cost remains inconclusive. The technology additionally exhibits a deficiency in a clearly defined risk/reward proposition, leading to a dearth of openness in the process of decision-making. To ensure the successful adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) technologies, it is imperative to prioritize finance and risk management.

4.2. Research Inference

The overall survey was done in line with the aim of this dissertation following both positivism and interpretivism research philosophy (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). Positivism because there is a positive outlook of the theory based on the hypothesis that artificial intelligence and machine learning technology would have the same positive impact on data center operations in other information technology spheres. Since this is not a technical research paper, the

questionnaire was drafted in line with knowing the perception of the XYZ critical operations team about the impact of the introduction of the technology into their complex facility operations.

The result of the questions shows that the team believes the technology could improve the work way things are done as well as improve the various data center metrics like the PUE, WUE, CUE and efficiency. When asked if the team believes that AI and ML technology would improve their facility's efficiency, 92% of the respondents are very positive about this. Also, the 82% yes response on the question of the possibility of AI being a useful tool in their data center operations as well as the 70.6% positive response on the question of whether they would trust AI to make operational decisions in their data center corroborates with the hypothesis of this study.

There are however some concerns on the part of the organization's readiness for the implementation of the technology based on the present setup. 76.5% of the operations team believes the existing data collected would not be adequate for the implementation of AI, 64.7% believe the IT team is not adequately staffed to support the technology and 94.1% believe that budget would be a constraint.

4.3. Recommendation.

The following recommendations are proposed if XYZ would be willing to implement this technology based on the findings of this study.

1. IT staff should be adequately trained to improve their knowledge of the technology if there is time is an advantage. Another alternative is to recruit a team specifically to support the deployment and operations of the technology.
2. There should be a budget provision for the experimentation and as well as the deployment of the technology looking at the improvement it could bring into their operations.
3. Improvement in equipment monitoring to make more data available for building AI and ML models.

5. Conclusion

The data center industry has been growing bigger year on year due to the new appetite for digitization among users of the applications they support. Research conducted by Technavio in early 2021 shows that the data center market is poised to increase by USD 519.34 billion through 2021-2025, increasing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of over 21% during the forecasted period (Maida, 2021). This growth has introduced a lot of complexity into their operations and made the traditional method of running the facility's operations insufficient. The industry must evolve in the way they do things in line with the growth of the industry and the multi-equipment operations. AI and ML technology has witnessed success in many industrial spaces in the way it has brought improvement to their various complex operations. This paper looked at the possibility of replication of this positive impact that AI technology has in other industries in the data center industry.

Research was carried out on XYZ Data Center due to the advantage of the ease of access to information based on my relationship with the organization. The research was a mixed method of qualitative and quantitative as survey questions were sent out to the participants. The questions were dichotomous with a follow-up question asking for further explanation to better understand the reasoning behind the different choices.

The result aligns with the hypothesis of the research paper as seen from the result analysis that participants believe the adoption of artificial intelligence and machine learning in XYZ's data center operations would have a positive impact on the efficiency, safety, security, sustainability, and all other aspects of their operations. The recommendations of what was needed to get the organization to the level of technology implementation based on the analysis of the findings were spelt out and the organization can leverage this in their future decision process.

This paper mainly consulted this study to understand the XYZ's critical operation team's perception of the technology as well as gauge the acceptability of the same. There is still a need for future experimental research to get a holistic and more practical contribution that AI and ML could have on their operations.

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7. Appendix

Link to survey result:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScntLxTgKO13yD_fSilj29jdSxALLga-ZBlvINXyZpDAovNsA/viewform?usp=sharing

If yes, what are the areas within your operations that you think this technology would be useful?

14 responses

In making decisions about mechanical infrastructure

Optimizing SOOs / BMS tweaks

For mechanical systems, further tuning to optimize energy and operational efficiency. For electrical systems, performing risk and impact analysis for failed components.

Chiller plant operations, generator controls, lighting controls

I think AI could be useful in identifying trends in data gathered by BMS systems and making recommendations for changes that could improve reliability and efficiency.

Environmental Controls (BAS), workflow creation and management, communications, data analytics.

Counter-intuitive energy efficiency, resiliency, reduced equipment downtime due to preventative and corrective maintenance

Chemical water treatment, oil samples, weather and outside air conditions.

What are the areas in your data center operations that you think AI or ML can bring improvement?

14 responses

I think that mechanical infrastructure would benefit the most of AI and ML, given that mechanical systems are usually reactive to the load and weather condition changes.

power load monitoring and precision cooling

Facility security, scheduling for preventive maintenance, operational procedures.

Optimizing SOOs / BMS tweaks

Mechanical system efficiency

chiller plant controls

Environmental Controls (BAS), workflow creation and management, communications, data analytics, event management.

Counter-intuitive energy efficiency, resiliency, reduced equipment downtime due to preventative and corrective maintenance

Would you trust AI/ML to make operational decisions in your data center?

17 responses

If yes, to what extent would you allow?

12 responses

I'd allow decision making as long as my operations team is aware of those via emails and BMS screen

To a point but I will always have the ability to override if needed.

It could suggest things such as scheduling preventive maintenance on equipment, maintain schedules on operations procedures that need to be completed, and assist with facility security.

Approved by an operator prior to implementation.

Yes, assuming that the scope of change is minimized. The starting point for an AI/ML based operation should be a decision engine that provides ideas and suggestions to the human operators.

low impacting changes, communications and escalation workflows.

Control of systems within a set of rules/guidelines with the ML system operating as a supervised closed loop system, notifications for non-optimal systems

Return to utility after an outage.

If no, why not?

6 responses

No, because the technology hasn't been proven on a large scale critical operation. Little track record exists to trust an AI/ML system to fully operate a data center with limited human intervention.

I would have to use it for lower risk operational decisions first and gradually incorporate it into higher risk

I would have to use it for lower risk operational decisions first and gradually incorporate it into higher risk activities.

In my research, AI seems to make decisions without providing a comprehensible reason for the decision. That dramatically increases the chance that a decision could be made that could negatively impact operations without the ability to understand why the decision was made.

I would still want dual verification of some sort

Maybe I dont know enough about AI to say for sure, but in a DC it needs to react to the current conditions and not what is expected.

Not familiar with it, and would need to see it in action first.

17 responses

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- 5. Do you think AI and ML can improve your data center's energy efficiency?
- Yes
- No

If yes, how do you think this can improve efficiency?

16 responses

Again on mechanical infrastructure, I think, but it'd be interesting to see if AI would come up with some new idea to improve efficiency on the electrical infrastructure.

Because it can consider many factors and develop a solution based on facts with data behind it, unlike humans, there are no human feelings behind the decision; everything is based upon data.

Proper maintenance on equipment can reduce downtime, ensure that the equipment is operating at nominal standards and also forecast the need to replace aging or end of life equipment

Optimizing equipment setpoints, SOO programming, etc.

More efficient mechanical plant operation

Optimize usage during peak loads and outside weather conditions.

Identifying data trends that could guide changes in operation.

If no, why not?

1 response

In a DC it needs to react to the current conditions and not what is expected.

Do you think AI and ML improve your data center's sustainability?

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17 responses

If yes, how do you think this can be achieved?

13 responses

If we have AI and ML for some time collecting data from various designs and systems, I think eventually it'd come up with interesting sustainable equipment selection and maybe design changes.

It can consider things that humans may miss.

AI could use PUE, CUE and WUE metrics to ensure that the facility is using resources efficiently and within limits.

More efficient use of energy in the mechanical plant equals a more sustainable data center.

It will lower energy usage where possible.

In the sense that it could lead to better efficiency, yes. I think the industry as a whole lacks a clear idea of what sustainability is or would look like.

An AI can analyze large data sets and propose changes in seconds that has traditionally taken a human or team months to accomplish. The AI/ML will need access to all available systems and their data sets.

If no, why not?

If no, why not?

3 responses

In my opinion it is more about a human behaviour.

In a DC it needs to react to the current conditions and not what is expected.

Most sustainability initiatives are driven by the use of new materials and technology rather than process or data. If the data center is more efficient it would technically help with sustainability, but that is not how the public measures sustainability.

Do you think AI and ML will improve your asset performance management process?

 Copy

17 responses

If yes, how do you think this can be achieved?

15 responses

If AI could predict failures on certain components within my critical equipment and advise me to purchase a certain part number ahead of time.

Because assets will be used based on data performance and will be adjusted accordingly, this way, assets like CRAHs and Chiller will be utilized in the most efficient way.

AI would be able to use power ratings on servers and network equipment to ensure that energy usage was efficient and could be used to reduce energy consumption during periods of low usage by the equipment.

ML could be used for condition-based maintenance and effective lifecycle replacement analysis (e.g. has the cost of repairing system x outgrown the cost of replacing it).

Help predict equipment problems and failures before they happen.

By identifying factors that impact reliability and could improve useful life of assets

An AI can analyze large data sets and propose changes in seconds that has traditionally taken a human or team months to accomplish. The AI/ML will need access to all available systems and their data sets.

If no, why not?

2 responses

Only if significant investments are made in monitoring technology. Without individual component data of parameters not necessarily available via BMS, there is not enough data to monitor and optimize equipment PM schedules.

In a DC it needs to react to the current conditions and not what is expected.

Would AI and ML technology deployment improve your site's security?

 Copy

17 responses

If yes, what areas of your physical security do you think this technology can improve?

10 responses

AI can monitor many cameras and utilize tools such as access control if there is a legitimate threat in the area.

In combination of RFID technology, AI would ensure that employees and customers could only access areas that they were authorized to enter and restrict other areas only authorized personnel.

Intrusion detection, possibly.

Security systems are already using AI to identify objects to determine if they're a risk or not (e.g. is that a person by the front gate or is it wildlife).

By identifying threats to security while reducing the number of false positives that existing tech creates.

Guards can zone out, fall asleep. AI doesn't do either of these.

Possibly watch the building during nights when low supervision is required

AI and ML technology deployment can indeed improve the security of a site or facility by enhancing threat

If no, why not?

6 responses

I don't see how AI could improve site security or make it to be more proactive.

Until bias can be removed from AI/ML, it will assess and propose solutions with bias against people. There are multiple examples across the globe on why AI used for security is not good.

I can't think of anything where ML would improve site security.

There are several aspects of human behaviour we could not predict and it would create a bias of certain types of people.

In a DC it needs to react to the current conditions and not what is expected.

Cant see security getting more complex than the current deterrents currently in place. I havent seen any industry incorporate AI and ML into their security plan.

Do you think AI and ML technology deployment can improve your organization's customer experience?

 Copy

17 responses

If yes, what aspect of your process do you think this can improve?

10 responses

The only area I can think of is if AI would receive and understand clearly a customer remote hands request and designate a technician to perform that activity with all information needed. That'd make response time faster and in consequence, better customer experience.

AI can improve customer experience because it can monitor things that are reported in surveys and also social media. This way, AI can adjust items it can control that customers may find pleasing as they perform business with your company.

If no, why not?

6 responses

Not sure how this would be applicable.

I cant think of anything that would directly impact customer satisfaction.

I think this would take away from the human touch

In my opinion, this is more a face to face experience.

In a DC it needs to react to the current conditions and not what is expected.

Customer service is delivered by people and process. I could be convinced otherwise if shown where it can help.

Do you think an AI and ML technology implementation in data center operations would improve operator safety?

[Copy](#)

17 responses

If yes, how do you think this can be implemented to improve safety?

13 responses

Advising operator of existing hazards and or conditions of equipment would improve operator safety.

Again, AI can detect things faster than a human and make changes as it see fit for the safety of the people.

AI could be used to monitor equipment that is down for maintenance and ensure that it is not improperly activated while it is being worked on. It can also be used to monitor workers remotely in case an emergency occurs and medical assistance should be contacted.

Maybe. I think that there are opportunities both for safety improvement but also increased safety risk